

8T – The Coupling Constants Series Unbounded Quarks

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Abstract:

By analyzing the primordial coupling constants series in its first representation, i.e. net curvature, it is possible to construct a situation in which the sea of gluons vanishes, leading to unbounded Quarks. Whether it is possible in the real world it unknown. The vanishing of the sea of gluons is via an inverse set of Gluons, isomorphic in size.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matrix tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matrix tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.21). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We presented recently the EMT symmetry by the terms (1.45) and (1.46):

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (\mu^-)] + \gamma \quad (1.45)$$

In addition, the Tau:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (\tau^-)] + \gamma \quad (1.46)$$

Up until now, reader is probability familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T thesis fundamentals. From here on out, we have a completely new paper. Since it was proven that fermions are described by the term:

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.47)$$

It was possible to construct the visualization of Quark confinement as the following:

The question is whether it is possible to create a scenario in which the Quark elements in the triplet is unbound. Suppose that the amount of net curvature of the first coupling term is constant, that the sea of Gluons is of finite size over time. If that assumption to hold true we can parametrize the sea of Gluons:

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta(+1)_i = K \quad (1.48)$$

$$\frac{\partial K}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.49)$$

If we accept as an axiom that the Quarks triplet is bounded by the sea of Gluons, which is finite in size. Than in order to examine Quarks as free particles, there has to be a vanishing of the net curvature or the sea of Gluons. The vanishing can be presented by an inverse set of elements, which in physics is regarded as Anti-matter. Curvature in the orthogonal direction, in such way that the inner product of the two curvatures is zero.

$$\langle \delta g_i | -\delta g_i \rangle = 0 \quad (1.50)$$

Given the asymmetry in between anti-matter to matter and the over simplistic assumption of the sea of Gluons to stay as it is over time, ignoring the fact that each net curvature increasing the probability of arrival to its position on the matric tensor, it is very unlikely that such a phenomena of unbounded Quarks can be observed. That is given by two reasons, the first, if the sea is in fact finite, there must be a way to count how many Gluons are presented in between the Triplet. The second, than, we will need to find a way to take the exact inverse amount of anti-particles and inject it into the sea of Gluons, to eliminate it. As far as we understand, generating anti-particles in infinitesimal amount is almost beyond our technological reach, let alone multi-particle set. That being said, ignoring those complexities of the real world, theoretically if (1.49) is correct, it should be possible, given advanced enough technology.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)